

CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRACTICES IN THE BULGARIAN RAW MATERIAL INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT. The circular economy, which promotes the responsible and cyclical use of resources, contributing to sustainable development is becoming more and more popular, especially in the European Union. The concept of switching from the traditional linear to cyclical consumption model leads to minimisation of waste and environmental pollution, and in this regard the New Circular Economy Plan is already in place. The great ambitions for changes in the industry are strengthened by the Green Pact (Green Deal).

The publication presents an in-depth study of the literature on the subject, as well as the five business models through which, in practice, a circle is realised. It has been established that the literature in the context of the mining industry is extremely scarce, and the business models through which the processes in the industry are carried out are poorly studied. An up-to-date survey of 13 companies in the raw-material resources sector in Bulgaria is also presented, aimed at showing the extent to which they understand and apply the circular economy in their work. The results unequivocally prove that the concept is not new for the business.

Keywords: circular economy, business models, raw material industry

Historical view of the term "Circular economy"

Today, the Circular Economy provides basic guidelines about what needs to be done to significantly and permanently reduce the resource dependence of the economy and to move towards overcoming the scarcity of non-renewable natural resources. It offers important solutions, especially related to production and design skills, new business models, cycle building skills, and cross-industry collaboration. The circular economy is a closed cycle covering each of the three areas: supply and responsible choice of producers, consumer demand and behaviour, and waste management (Europesworld, 2014).

The circular economy has different meanings for the different participants in various areas. Common denominators are waste design and pollution (waste reduction), maintenance of products and materials in use (increase in scale and keeping the value), regenerate natural systems, (loops, transition) and social aspect such as well-being (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017).

Retrospectively, the term "circular economy" has a rich historical past on the basis of various schools of thought, such as "industrial ecology", "cradle to cradle", "efficient economy", "blue economy" and "biomimicry". The current meaning of the term is built on all of these concepts, each of which has contributed to its further improvement and development, such as "cradle to cradle", implies an endless cycle of the resource use, biomimetics or adaptation of naturally occurring forms in technology, natural capital - approach to environmental assessment, etc. All these concepts reinforce the idea of the circular economy, namely its goal - to extend the life cycle of resources by minimising the use of goods resulting in non-recyclable waste.

One of the founders of the idea is Alfred Marshall, who in 1890 introduced the concept of "Industrial Areas" - areas with high concentration of workers and companies specialising in the basic industry and auxiliary industries. Later, George Renner (1947) put in the term "industrial symbiosis," describing the exchange of residual materials as water and energy, and mentioning the possibility of companies exchanging waste as raw materials, describing the interrelationships that occur in nature as symbioses.

The first studies of the impact of consumer products on the environment appeared in the 1960s, mainly in a comparative context.

In 1966, Kenneth Boulding first introduced the concept of closed systems, envisaging a future economy that would function by reproducing the limited supply of waste and recycling waste.

The published Meadows's report (1972) "The Limits of Growth", underlines the limit of resources of the planet Earth. For the first time, a research team presented in this study scenarios based on computer modelling to stimulate interactions between populations, food production, industrial production, pollution and the consumption of non-renewable energy sources.

Despite its historical past, many scientists suppose that the term "circular system" was officially introduced into the economic model of Pearce and Turner (1990), who built their theoretical framework on the research of environmental economist Kenneth Boulding. In their study, Pearce and Turner offer a critical look at the traditional linear economic system and develop a new economic model that applies the principles of thermodynamics. In their paper "Economics of Natural Resources and the Environment" they outline the theories in and between the economics of natural resources and the implications for the concept of how the economy works. The authors consider the environment both as an entrance and as a receiver of waste. They indicate that neglecting the environment means ignoring the economy, as it is a linear or open system without a built-in recycling system. However, an extensive review of the literature over the last two decades has shown that the origins of the circular economy are rooted mainly in the environmental economy or in industrial ecology (Rizos et al., 2017).

Following Pearce and Turner, many authors have attempted to define the circular economy by providing resource-oriented definitions and / or interpretations, emphasizing the need to create closed circuits of material flows and reduce environmental impacts.

Thus, according to Preston (2012), "the circular economy is an approach that would transform the function of resources into the economy. Factory waste will be a valuable contribution to another process - and products can be repaired, reused or upgraded instead of disposed of".

Mitchell (2015) goes further and emphasizes the importance in the circular economy of conserving resources for as long as possible, as well as extracting maximum value from products and materials by using them for as long as possible and then recovering and using them again.

Sauvé et al. (2016) suggest that the circular economy refers to "the production and consumption of goods through a closed loop of material flows that internalise the external environmental impacts associated with the extraction of clean resources and the generation of waste (including pollution)". According to them, the main focus of the circular economy is to reduce resource consumption, pollution and waste at every step of the product life cycle.

There are also several interpretations of the concept in the available literature that try to go beyond the concept of material resource management and include additional dimensions. For example, Heck (2006) argues that in the debate on the circular economy, the use of sustainable energy has not yet succeeded in gaining equal status compared to recycling and waste management. For this goal, he suggests that the transition to a circular economy will require tackling the challenge of establishing a sustainable energy supply, as well as taking decisive action in several other areas such as agriculture, water, soil and biodiversity (Rizos et al., 2017).

According to the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, the circular economy aims to redefine growth by looking beyond the current industrial waste model. The focus is on the benefits to society and on the gradual separation of economic activity from the consumption of limited resources, while reducing waste and ultimately projecting it outside the system. The circular model builds economic, natural and social capital, supported by the transition to renewable energy sources (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017).

To facilitate the transition to an efficient circular economy, at the end of 2015 the European Commission adopted a package of measures to increase the global competitiveness of the European economy and protect limited resources, creating a level playing field for all actors. The package includes an action plan in the areas of product design, production processes, consumption, waste management, innovation and investment in plastics, food waste, raw materials, construction waste, biomass and legislative proposals on waste to reduce landfill, increase reuse and recycling.

The transition to a circular economy is a huge opportunity to transform our economy so that it is more sustainable and thus contribute to climate goals and the conservation of global resources, job creation and competitive development advantages for Europe. The transition to a circular economy will also help meet the goals set in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

The new plan for a circular economy, which builds on what was achieved in 2015 - the European Green Pact, follows this trend. The green deal that gives a clear direction - a carbon-neutral and circular economy by 2050, and for this purpose it is expected to be adopted in the so-called Climate law. The focus on the circular economy is not accidental - 45% of the global greenhouse gas emissions are "invested" in products. These are the emissions during their production, as well as during the extraction and transport of the materials from which they are made (Paspaldzhiev, 2020).

Business models in the circular economy

The rapid deterioration of the world's environment has led to the development of policies to reduce the negative impact of production and consumption. A number of countries have introduced acts and laws establishing the principle of recycling or the circular economy.

Almas Heshmati (2015) traces the first countries that introduced the concept of a circular economy at the state level. According to him, Germany is the first in this, since it started implementing the circular economy in 1996, although it had worked in this direction long before that. This act is accompanied by the entry into force of the Closed Cycle of Substances and the Waste Management Act. The law provides a framework for the implementation of closed-cycle waste management and provides environmentally compatible waste disposal and assimilative waste capacity. Another example of an attempt to start implementing the circular economy is in Japan. The Japanese government has developed a comprehensive legal framework for the country's transition to a recycling-based society (METI, 2004; Morioka et al., 2005).

The Basic Law on the Establishment of a Recycling-Based Society, which came into force in 2002, provides quantitative targets for recycling and long-term dematerialisation of Japanese society (Van Berkel et al., 2009).

China is the third country which makes serious efforts to widely implement a circular economy. However, unlike in Germany and Japan, the Chinese government, for various reasons, such as maintaining competitiveness, initially introduced the framework of the circular economy on a smaller scale through a series of pilot studies so as to have a better basis for assessing its large scale and full coverage in the long run. This policy is similar to economic liberalisation, which began with economic free zones. Several other countries, such as Sweden, have long been consistently introducing various incentive programmes in an attempt to facilitate the optimal conditions for gradually and effectively increasing the rate of recycling through public education. The policy is successful and satisfies politicians and environmentalists (Heshmati et al., 2015).

When a business invests in value creation, long-term, sustainable and competitive economic value is achieved (Trifonova, 2019).

In the circular economy, production and consumption are increasingly based on the use of services instead on the possession of material goods. Companies are changing their operational models as well as updating their operations to support climate change mitigation (Sitra, 2019b).

The circular business model is an economic model in which consumption is based on the use of services - sharing, renting and recycling, instead of owning and producing more and more goods. In the end, the materials are not destroyed, but are used as a basis for new products and this process is repeated again and again (Sitra, 2019a).

The practical realisation of the circle in the economy happens through different business models. The Finnish innovation fund Sitra considers 5 business models (Fig. 1), namely: renewables; sharing platforms; product as a service; prolonging the life of the product; resource efficiency and recycling.

Fig. 1. "Circular value chain", Jyri Arponen, Sitra Finnish Innovation Fund, <https://www.slideshare.net/SitraEkologia/jyri-arponen-circular-economy-playbook>

Product Life Extension - allows companies to extend product and asset lifecycle. The value that would otherwise be lost from worn-out materials is instead maintained or even improved through repair, renovation and recycling.

The product as a service - the manufacturer remains the owner of the product and provides only the service as an alternative to the traditional model of "buy and own". The products are used by one or more customers through a rental agreement or payment for use.

Resource efficiency and recycling (Circular supply) - provides fully renewable, recyclable or biodegradable resources, which are the basis of circular production and

consumption systems by replacing raw materials with biological raw materials (renewable, recyclable and biodegradable) of ecodesign.

Utilisation of waste resources - allows companies to eliminate leakage of materials and maximise the economic value of product returns.

Sharing platforms - promotes platforms for cooperation and shared use of products between users - individuals or organisations.

Circular business models open up the value chain for new collaborations and services enabling bottom line impact (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. "Circular sub-models", Juri Arponen, Sitra the Finnish Innovation Fund, <https://www.slideshare.net/SitraEkologia/jyri-arponen-circular-economy-playbook>

Business models from the circular economy in the raw material industry in Bulgaria

According to data from the Bulgarian Chamber of Mining and Geology in 2017, the total value of production of industrial enterprises in the mining industry amounted to BGN 2,85 billion (around 1,45 billion EURO), which is an increase compared to previous years.

The number of people employed in the mining industry in 2019 is 20 779 people, and the trend is insignificant compared to previous years.

The raw material industry is a specific one because the number of operating enterprises is relatively small, but they still manage to generate output and added value, which in absolute terms exceeds the production of many other industries.

The graph in Fig. 3 traces the pace of production since 2010, broken down by sub-sector. Each sub-sector has a relatively stable pace, as traditionally the highest productivity is in the sub-sectors "Mining of ore materials", "Coal mining" and "Mining of industrial materials (non-metallic)", as the total extraction of the raw and energy (coal) materials in our country in 2018 was in the amount of 108,42 million tonnes and there is a slight decrease compared to the previous year.

Fig. 3. Raw materials production by sub-sector, in thousand tonnes

The examples of waste-free production in Bulgaria are becoming more and more, as the mining industry is among the leaders in the field of circular economy. For the sector, the situation is slightly different from the traditional one - material flows are usually large and concentrated and therefore the useful use of waste occurs much more often. Given the specifics of the activity, the business models that have been proven to be applicable are "Resource efficiency and recycling" and "Waste resource recovery".

An example in the circular economy is one of the best underground mines in the world - Dundee Precious Metals Chelopech. In 2005, the so-called chamber system was introduced with the subsequent filling of the seized mining spaces with hardening material, which includes all sterile rock masses and a large part of the flotation waste mixed with cement.

In Assarel Medet an oxide embankment (a hill formed by the disposal of oxide copper ores, once treated as waste) is simultaneously reclaimed and operated through a drainage system for catching and draining water to be directed to the production of cathode copper or treatment plants. Lavender is grown on the reclaimed land for oil production and honey is also extracted at the same time.

Survey results

At the beginning of 2020, in connection with INTERREG Europe project "REDUCES", a survey was conducted among the companies from the Bulgarian mining industry, in order to establish the understanding and application of the models for circular economy. The survey was provided to 65 companies in the business, with only 13 of them participating in its completion.

The analysis of the results shows that in most of the surveyed companies circular models for modernisation and innovation are applied, namely:

- Opportunity for efficient processing of poor ores;
- Industrial water supply in a closed cycle to supply the production process;
- Mounting of an installation for extraction and electrowinning of cathode copper from mine water, through which an additional by-product is obtained - pure copper;
- Technology for extraction of accompanying gold in copper concentrate, so that precious components are not lost in the waste;
- Application of a method of extraction, which includes backfilling, i.e. the ground sterile rock mass is returned to the underground mine in the form of a pasty filling, is an example of a circular economy, which not only reduces the amount of waste deposited on the surface, but is also used the waste as a raw material, which is mixed with cement and returned to the seized chambers, ensuring the stability of the rock massif;
- Use of part of the mine ballast for filling the used spaces underground, for paving during the construction of the underground roads after crushing and for upgrading the walls of the tailings pond;
- In the extraction of limestone, necessary for the production of lime, many additional fractions of material are released, which are not discarded, but sifted and placed on the market for aggregates;
- Use of earth masses and sludge for reclamation of disturbed terrains;
- Delivery to specialised companies of used oils for recycling and use in other industries;
- Recycling of metals used for drilling tool crowns;
- Separate collection of waste and its transfer for specialised treatment.

Conclusion

The transition to a circular economy is determined by the argument that the linear model: extraction-production-consumption-waste is not sustainable because it requires continuous extraction of new raw materials.

In the context of the topic, Bulgaria lags behind, especially in terms of technologies for recycling and waste treatment. Knowledge is needed for fast and efficient use of technologies, as our country has the potential to introduce innovative waste policies.

The mineral resources industry, although poorly represented in the study, is prepared to meet the challenges of the concept and proves that it manages waste as a raw material.

Public policies, in the context of the EU's common policies in the field of the circular economy and the environment, are complex, difficult and multifaceted. All this requires going through many consultations and discussions, negotiations and legislative changes, as well as the engagement of a wide range of professional expertise. The state mechanism should be activated by stating its active state position and policy to strengthen the regulatory environment that favours the implementation of socially responsible practices, as well as the management of financial instruments for support.

Acknowledgments. This study is a part of project "REDUCES", PGI06140 financed by INTERREG Europe Programme.

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